

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-290-IE-5% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20230403
Vial:	102	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 290
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	274.0nm
Run Time:	18.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 274.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	4/3/2023 9:50:28 PM CST		
Date Processed:	4/4/2023 9:36:08 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.278	163141	16.79	21703
2	6.692	158270	16.29	19489
3	8.444	323134	33.26	30731
4	14.365	326958	33.65	17987

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-291-IE-5% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20230403
Vial:	103	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 291
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	274.0nm
Run Time:	18.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 274.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	4/3/2023 10:09:08 PM CST		
Date Processed:	4/4/2023 9:37:57 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.287	20751	1.86	2905
2	6.701	4953	0.44	581
3	8.531	596	0.05	112
4	14.277	1090413	97.64	55822